

ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF MODERN SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND TRAINING

KHOREZMSCIENCE.UZ

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UNIVERSAL METHODS OF CLASSIFICATION OF VIOLENCE AGAINST PEOPLE WITH DISABILITIES

Ziyaeva Khalida Amonkul Kizi

*Associate Professor of Sociology (PhD),
Mirzo Ulugbek National University of
Uzbekistan*

holidaziyaeva@gmail.com

Annotatsiya. Jahonda aholi soning oshib borishi bilan aholining tarkibiy qismida bo‘lgan nogironligi bo‘lgan shaxslarning soni ham oshib bormoqda. Nogironligi bo‘lgan shaxslar jismoniy yoki ruhiy sabablar bilan bog‘liq ravishda atrof-muhit bilan o‘zaro munosabatga ko‘ra o‘z huquqlarini mustaqil ravishda amalga oshirish va himoya qilishda ko‘plab qiyinchiliklarga duch keladilar. Shuning uchun ham nogironligi bo‘lgan shaxslar davlat va jamiyatning alohida muhofazasiga muhtoj hisoblanadilar. Nogironligi bo‘lgan shaxslar soni aholining katta qismini tashkil etishi ham ular uchun teng huquq va imkoniyatlarni ta‘minlash masalasiga ko‘proq e‘tibor qaratish zarurligini ko‘rsatadi. Bunday vaziyatlar dunyo mamlakatlarining ijtimoiy jarayonlariga ta‘sir ko‘rsatib, mamlakatning ichki va tashqi siyosatiga hamda ijtimoiy tartibotlarini o‘zgarishiga olib kelmoqda. Bunday jarayonlar bir tarafdin mamlakatning ijtimoiy tuzilmalar faoliyatiga ta‘sir ko‘rsatayotgan bo‘lsa, ikkinchi tarafdin nogironligi bo‘lgan shaxslarning ijtimoiy himoyasiga va ularning turli zo‘ravonliklarga duch kelishiga sharoitni keltirib chiqarmoqda.

Kalit so‘zlar: *inson huquqlari, nogironligi bo‘lgan shaxslar, xotin-qizlar, psixologik, jismoniy, jinsiy, iqtisodiy zo‘ravonlik, kamsitish, disabilizm, eybilizm, mentalizm.*

Аннотация. С ростом численности населения мира увеличивается и количество людей с ограниченными возможностями в составе населения. Инвалиды сталкиваются со многими трудностями при самостоятельном осуществлении и защите своих прав в связи с взаимодействием с окружающей средой по физическим или психическим причинам. Именно

поэтому инвалиды нуждаются в особой защите государства и общества. Тот факт, что инвалиды составляют значительную часть населения, также указывает на необходимость уделять больше внимания вопросу обеспечения им равных прав и возможностей. Подобные ситуации влияют на социальные процессы стран мира и приводят к изменениям во внутренней и внешней политике и общественном порядке страны. Подобные процессы, с одной стороны, влияют на функционирование социальных структур страны, а с другой – создают условия для социальной защиты лиц с ограниченными возможностями и их подверженности различным формам насилия.

Ключевые слова: права человека, инвалиды, женщины, психологическое, физическое, сексуальное, экономическое насилие, дискриминация, инвалидность, эйблизм, ментализм.

Abstract. With the increase in the world population, the number of persons with disabilities in the composition of the population is also increasing. Persons with disabilities face many difficulties in the independent exercise and protection of their rights in relation to their interaction with the environment due to physical or mental reasons. That is why persons with disabilities need special protection of the state and society. The fact that the number of persons with disabilities constitutes a large part of the population also indicates the need to pay more attention to the issue of ensuring equal rights and opportunities for them. Such situations affect the social processes of the countries of the world and lead to changes in the country's internal and external policy and social order. Such processes, on the one hand, affect the functioning of the country's social structures, and on the other hand, create conditions for the social protection of persons with disabilities and their exposure to various forms of violence.

Keywords: human rights, persons with disabilities, women, psychological, physical, sexual, economic violence, discrimination, disability, ableism, mentalism.

Introduction

According to the data published by the Population Division of the Department of Economic and Social Affairs of the United Nations Secretariat on January 1, 2024, “The world's population will reach 8 billion on November 15, 2022, and almost a third of them, i.e. 33.2%, will be the population with social needs” [1]. According to the World Health Organization, 1.3 billion people in the world have a disability, which is about one in six of the world's population. If we look at the international level from the point of view of layers and social classes, people with disabilities constitute the largest minority group [2].

In New Uzbekistan, special attention is paid to the provision of targeted social services to persons with disabilities, who are considered to be the neediest segment of the population, registered in the “Iron Register”, “Youth Register” and “Women’s Register”. Special attention is paid to ensuring the rights and legal interests of citizens with disabilities in order to further strengthen the principles of kindness, benevolence and generosity in our society. The most important thing is that this system should work in practice and people of this category should feel that they are full members of the

society, his words have become the content of systematic work on social and legal protection of persons with disabilities in our country [3].

Literature Review

The views on the origin of the phenomenon of violence were given by the classical sociologist Emile Durkheim in his “Method of Sociology”. E. Durkheim in his research on the evaluation of crime, “Violence can have some positive aspects along with its negative aspects. For this reason, society should pay attention to the presence of a favorable situation or environment for committing a crime. Because it is necessary to recognize that the philosophical category prevails that without necessity, causation does not occur” [4]. Canadian sociologist Lee John Alan also expressed a similar opinion, in his opinion: Crime should exist for society as one of its important components, crime is evil and violence. “If there is no form of evil and violence in society, then people do not know the meaning and value of goodness and well-being” [5].

In our opinion, when the issue of violence in sociology is considered within the framework of social stratification, violence can be interpreted as the cause of inequality in power relations, because violence means the dominance of a strong person over a weak person. The strong rule over the weak. For this reason, a strong person is unequaled by his physical or intellectual strength.

M. Weber emphasized that violence can occur at different levels of power in society and state management. He believed that legitimate rule was based on tradition, charisma, that is, the ability of a person to appeal to the hearts of other people intellectually, spiritually, or otherwise, or on legal principles [6].

The classical sociologist Talcott Parsons also made a significant contribution to the sociological study of the relationship between violence and the cause of prosperity or unrest for the community or family. In his theory of structural-functionalism, he stated that since the family is the only source of society, this social institution is an important and basic institution for society [7]. T. Parsons also believed that individuals in all social institutions, such as the family, properly fulfill their social functions and roles as a prevention of violence.

Research Methodology.

In this article, the sociological analysis of approaches to the detection of violence against persons with disabilities, using content analysis and comparative methods, allows to determine the manifestations of violence and the specific characteristics of being a victim of violence of these persons.

Analysis and Results

Initially, in Western European literature on sociology and social work, disability was defined as a person who has partially or completely lost the ability to work due to war, illness or injury. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Rights of Persons with Disabilities” adopted on October 15, 2020 on the protection of the rights of persons with disabilities in our country [8]. The adoption and ratification of the “Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities” (New York, December 13, 2006) on June 7, 2021 clearly defines the socio-legal status of persons with disabilities in Uzbekistan, allowing them to express themselves as equal members of society in all areas [9].

Article 16 of the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities defines persons with disabilities in countries that have ratified this convention. Taking necessary measures to prevent all forms of exploitation, violence and aggression, including providing assistance and support to persons with disabilities, their families and caregivers, taking into account age and gender characteristics, including not being exposed to forms of exploitation, violence and aggression, will take all necessary measures to introduce the ways of identifying and reporting such cases, to increase their awareness in this matter. Participating states shall ensure that services for providing protection are provided taking into account age-sex characteristics and factors of disability [10].

Persons with disabilities often need positive conditions from society in order to have equal opportunities to participate in social processes. Because of this, they are more likely to experience violence. Such discriminatory unconscious behavior towards persons with disabilities can be evaluated as the beginning of violence [11].

Among persons with disabilities, women are at the highest risk of violence. This is especially the case of sexual violence against women. For women with disabilities, the lack of knowledge about sexual life, because they do not know that actions are sexual violence, they cannot distinguish violent behavior, such a situation creates conditions for the occurrence of sexual violence. Also, the inability of women with disabilities who are sexually assaulted to resist violence further encourages sexual assault.

According to a report by the European Union Parliament on June 26, 2022, almost 80 percent of women with disabilities are victims of violence and are four times more likely to experience sexual violence against other women. Research shows cases of forced sterilization of women with disabilities, especially women with intellectual disabilities, in several European countries, as well as in Asia, Australia, Latin America, and the Middle East [12].

Violence against persons with disabilities takes many forms in the global world. In particular, “Abilism” (eng. ableism) is a specific form of discrimination against persons with disabilities, which means denying them and rejecting their individuality [13]. For example, in a restaurant, when a waiter approaches customers to take orders, if one of the customers is a person with a disability, he or she will take the order to the non-disabled person accompanying him or her, rather than the person with a disability.

Another type of violence against persons with disabilities is called “disabilism”. The term was first used in the United Kingdom as a derogatory term for people with disabilities. This term is a severe form of ableism, and dysablism refers to the violent treatment and abusive behavior towards persons with disabilities [14].

Another type of violence against persons with disabilities is “Mentalism” (eng. mentalism), which is discrimination against persons with disabilities suffering from mental illnesses. It is often found among the employees of the medical institution [15].

Another form of violence against people with disabilities is called stigmatization. “Stigma” is a word derived from (Greek - Stigma) and means label, mark. For example, calling people with disabilities such words as blind, deaf, dumb, lame, garang, esipast, psycho is called stigma. One of the most widespread stigmatizations in society is the belief that people with one or another disability are mentally ill, and the lack of treatment is always a social danger [16].

Conclusions

In conclusion, the problems in protecting the rights of persons with disabilities are mostly related to violence. People with disabilities have the same human rights as other people, but the wrongly formed perceptions and views of people in society or the systemic problems that persist in society against people with disabilities and the limitations of physical capabilities of people with disabilities directly or indirectly discriminate against them, exclude them, as well as causes them to face violence.

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THEORICAL APPROACHES OF THE SOCIAL SUPPLY SYSTEM TO THE EASTERN SOCIAL THOUGHT

Tagieva Gulsum Gafurovna

*Associate Professor, Department
of Sociology and Social Affair,
Samarkand State University
Named after Sharof Rashidov
gt120886@gmail.com*

Annotatsiya. Ijtimoiy ta'minot masalasi sotsiologiyada fundamental muammolar sirasiga taalluqli bo'lib, uning tadqiqot tarixi uzoq o'tmishdan boshlanadi. Yaqin va O'rta Sharq mintaqasi olimlari o'z asarlarida himoya, obod va farovon jamiyat barpo etishga bag'ishlangan. Maqolada “ijtimoiy ta'minot” tushunchasi, Sharq ijtimoiy tafakkurida ijtimoiy himoya tizimlari asoslarini ishlab chiqqan buyuk mutafakkirlar Abu Nasr Forobiy va Ibn Haldunning sotsiologik qarashlari, yunon falsafasida Platon va Aristotelning asarlarida ijtimoiy siyosat nazariyasi, ijtimoiy ta'minot fenomeni haqidagi ta'limotlarining ahamiyati bugungi kun nuqtai nazaridan kelib chiqqan holda asoslab berilgan. Shuningdek, Markaziy Osiyo davlatlarida ijtimoiy ta'minot tizimini rivojlanishining zamonaviy tendensiyalari, zamonaviy ijtimoiy ta'minotning tuzilishi va uning o'zgarishiga ta'sir qiluvchi omillar, ijtimoiy ta'minot institutining shakllanishi va rivojlanishining tarixiy-sotsiologik tahlili bayon qilindi.

Kalit so'zlari: *Ijtimoiy ta'minot, ijtimoiy himoya, ijtimoiy ta'minotga oid ilmiy maktablar, O'zbekiston milliy sotsiologiya ilmiy maktabi.*

Аннотация. Проблема социальной безопасности является одной из фундаментальных проблем социологии, и история ее исследования начинается в далеком прошлом. Ученые региона Ближнего и Среднего Востока в своих работах посвящены построению безопасного, процветающего и процветающего общества. В статье рассмотрено понятие “социальная безопасность”, социологические взгляды великих мыслителей Абу Насра Фараби и Ибн Халдуна, разработавших основы систем социальной защиты в восточной социальной мысли, теория социальной политики в трудах Платона и Аристотель в греческой философии и значение их учения о явлении социального обеспечения обоснованы с сегодняшней точки зрения. Также были описаны современные тенденции развития системы социального обеспечения в странах Центральной Азии, структура современного социального обеспечения и факторы, влияющие на его изменение, проведен